

Excellent Service Activities Of Enji Multimedia Production House Company In Impression Building

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Abstract

Enji Multimedia Production House is a company that has been operating in the domain of service by manufacturing several programs such as games, animations, entertainments, and registration system by using high-end software. The intense competition within the manufacture of such programs has encouraged the Enji Multimedia Production House to improve its quality. One of the efforts that the Enji Multimedia Production House has attempted is to deliver the excellent service activities to the customers in building the company impression. In delivering such service, the Enji Multimedia Production House has a big commitment namely to build good and positive company impression before the customers. In this regard, the Enji Multimedia Production House demands a positive impression not only in the scope of the Asian market but also in the scope of the international market.

With reference to the previous paragraph, the company impression would like to be discussed in the present study is that there has been a need toward a deeper study on the aspect of excellent service activities delivery to the customers since the Enji Multimedia Production House has been building its company impression. In addition, the Enji Multimedia Production House has been sufficient in terms of organizational structure and competent employees in delivering the service to the customers since the company has been committed to provide the best service quality to the customers. Last but not the least, the excellent service that the Enji Multimedia Production has delivered is already satisfying and, thus, the customers sense that their needs have always been catered since the Enji Multimedia Production House has been prioritizing the customers in terms of needs and satisfaction.

Keyword : activities, excellent service, High Contact, Low Contact, service

INTRODUCTION

An organization always deals with the inter-individual relationship within its dynamics. Specifically, an organization always deals with the relationship among the stakeholders in the company. With reference to the statement, the role of public relations has high level of influence on the service activities that a company should deliver to the customers in order to gain their satisfaction. Up to date, public relations has been known to deal with the relationship between an organization and its surrounding community. Public relations appears to the surface because of the demand of the relationship between a company and its surrounding community. The statement implies that public relations has important function and duty that should be carried out namely developing a harmonious relationship between the management leadership and the employees and also between the company leadership and the company owners or vice versa. Similarly, public relations is expected to bridge or to establish communication with external communities since the external communities serve as the public that eventually will define the success or the failure of the company objective and the company impression that would like to be achieved.

Stakeholder involvement becomes an important aspect in establishing relevant relationship among numerous organizations within a single company. Not to mention, specific to the study, the stakeholder involvement in Enji Multimedia Production House becomes highly important for the management in delivering the positive values to the community. As a result, a company should listen to and discuss the issues in several aspects that draw the interest of both the organization's stakeholders and the inter-company strategic leaders. Thus, this context should be applied by any company that strives to establish excellent service in building the company impression. The statement also applies to Enji Multimedia Production since the Enji Multimedia Production itself is a company that operates within the manufacture of interactive

multimedia products such as games, animation, entertainment, and registration system by using the high-end tools.

The intense competition in the domain of production has urged Enji Multimedia Production to keep improving its quality. One of the improvement efforts that have been pursued is delivering the excellent service quality to the customers in building the company impression. With the excellent service delivery, it is expected that the sense of trust toward the company in terms of customer service might be improved. Indeed, due to the intense competition in gaining the market share among the customers, nowadays the service units of any institution has been demanded to be able to provide excellent service to the customers. In other words, service quality improvement should be pursued by any institution, including the government ones, in the form of excellent service delivery. Joko Widodo in Sugondo (2017, p.5) states that in order to provide excellent service the innovations in the public service are absolutely necessary in order that the public service delivery might be faster, better, and more affordable. As having been previously explained, excellent service has very vital role within the organization of a company so that the company might meet the customers' needs and eventually provide a sense of satisfaction among the customers.

One of the factors that should be considered within the excellent service delivery is customer satisfaction. According to Kotler (2005, p.70), customer satisfaction refers to the sense of being happy or being disappointed that appears within the internal aspect of an individual after comparing the perceived product performance (results) and the expected product performance (results). Looking at the definition, it is clear that every company should be able to cater the customer satisfaction by manufacturing products with better quality, lower price, faster delivery, and better service relative to the competitors.

The main objective of excellent service delivery is to deliver the type of service that meets or even exceeds the customer satisfaction or the public satisfaction as well as to deliver the focus of the service to the customers. The good customers in turn will be beneficial for the efforts of improving the government service quality to the public and, at the same time, the good customers might serve as the reference within the development of the service standards definition. In order to deliver the good service, there should be adherence toward the governing standards of public service within the government system. Based on the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment Decree Number 63 of 2003, the standards of public service include: (1) service procedures; (2) completion time; (3) service cost; (4) service product; (5) facilities; and (6) competence of service-delivery officers.

Within the activities of the excellent service delivery to its customers, the Enji Multimedia Production House has a great objective namely building good and positive impression before the customers. In this regard, the Enji Multimedia Production House demands a positive impression before not only the Asian customers but also the international customers. Thus, the present study is conducted in order to identify how the company, namely the Enji Multimedia Production House, builds its impression through the excellent service delivery to the customers.

The Enji Multimedia Production House has been selected because the company has been well-established in terms of organizational structure and competent employees within the excellent service delivery. In addition, the Enji Multimedia Production House has been striving to deliver the best quality in its service. Specific to the statement, the Enji Multimedia Production House has always prioritized the fulfillment of the customers' needs and satisfaction. Then, departing from the elaboration in the previous sections, the problems that will be formulated in the present study are as follows: (1) How does the Enji Multimedia Production perform its High Contact Service; (2) How does the Enji Multimedia Production performs its Low Contact Service; (3) How does the excellent service delivery influence the impression building of the Enji Multimedia Production; and (4) How does the Enji Multimedia Production proceed the impression branding within its excellent service delivery?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Communication Process

In this section, there will be a review on the corporate social responsibility, the corporate brand credibility, the corporate brand equity, and the corporate reputation. One of such review has been composed by Hur, Won-Woo, and Kim Hanna in their study under the title "How CSR Leads to Corporate Brand Equity: Mediating Mechanisms of Corporate Brand Credibility and Reputation" (Woo, Jeong, Nov. 2014). In relation to the statement, the objective of the study is identify the relationship among the corporate social

responsibility, the corporate brand credibility, the corporate brand equity, and the corporate reputation. Then, the structural equation model analysis is provided in order to support the hypothesis that has been drawn from 867 South Korean customers as the sample for their study. The results of their study show that the corporate social responsibility has direct positive impact toward the corporate brand and the corporate reputation.

In addition, the results of their study show that the corporate brand credibility mediates the relationship between the corporate social responsibility and the corporate reputation. In addition, the corporate brand credibility also mediates the relationship between the corporate social responsibility and the corporate reputation. Eventually, the relationship between the corporate social responsibility and the corporate brand equity is sequential and is completely mediated by the corporate brand credibility and the corporate reputation. In this regard, communication has strong association with the daily life of the people. Since the nature of communication is communicative, informative, and educative, automatically the exchange of message, science, and education as well as the persuasion of information is performed by means of communication. According to Hovland, Janis, & Kelly, Forsdale states that communication is process by which an individual transmits stimuli (usually verbal) to modify the behaviour of other individuals (Stephen W. Lillejohn, 2014, pp.3-4).

With regards to the above definition, Onong Uchjana Effendy suggests that the communication process is divided into two stages namely: (1) primary communication process; and (2) secondary communication process. Primary communication process refers to process of delivering the thoughts or the feelings of one individual to another by using symbols as the media. The symbols that serve as the primary media within the communication process are languages, idioms, parables, pictures, figures, colours, and any other symbols that might directly “interpret” the mind and/or the feelings of the communicator to the communicand. This process might take place in any place and at any time, including in an organization.

Organization Communication

Schein (1982) proposes that organization communication a rational coordination for the activities of a number of a people which aims at achieving several general objectives through the job division and the function by means of authority hierarchy and responsibility. With reference to the statement, organization displays certain characteristics namely: (1) having structure; (2) having objectives; (3) having inter-unit relationship; and (4) being dependent on human communication in order to coordinate the activities within the organization (Muhammad, 2008, p.23). Within the organization communication, or the company communication, there are several offers that the workers have made in order to promote the products or the facilities that their organization or company has. Such offers confirm that communication is an important and complex aspect within the life of the humankind. Not to mention, mankind is heavily influenced by the communication from one to another and by both the acquainted ones and the unacquainted ones.

Service Type

Nowadays, it is already common that a company or an organization provides well-qualified service to its customers. The reason is that the purchase decision of the customers is based on the strategic location, the affordable price, the interesting facilities, the marketing programs, and the brand or the service popularity (brand name). Service is a significant and uncontrollable factor. As a result, by means of comparison, many business competitors become prominent and distinguished only because of the service quality since the nature of service is emotional. In relation to this nature, service excellency refers to the capacity of anticipating, identifying, and fulfilling the expectations of the customers as well as being determined and attentive to exceed these expectations. While service might solely be defined as the fulfilment of the customers’ needs, in the context of service excellence service should be defined as the fulfilment and the exceeding of what the customers need and want.

Excellent Service

Excellent service is not a new term in employment, both the profit one and the non-profit one. The forms of excellent service are namely: (1) friendliness; (2) smile; (3) politeness; (4) timeliness; (5) accuracy; (6) openness; and (7) responsibility. Excellent service then might be defined as the best service or the great service since the delivery of the service has been adjusted to the standards that have been defined or been

organized by the given institutions. The essence of public service is excellent service delivery to the people, which has been the manifestation of the state apparatus' responsibilities as the civil servants (Solihin, 2012, p.24). Then, in this context, Supralan states that service might be defined as an action or a performance that one individual delivers to another. Furthermore, service might be classified in several categories as follows: (1) high contact service, namely the delivery of the service in which the contact between the customers and the service providers is very high; and (2) low contact service, namely the delivery of the service in which the contact between the customers and the service providers is not quite high (Waneri, 2011). With regards to the classification, the physical service with the customers that only takes place in the front desk might be classified as a low contact service (Waneri, 2011). Thus, customer expectation has a vital role in defining the product quality and the customer satisfaction. The customer will use his or her expectation as the standard or the reference in evaluating the success of the service delivery. In other words, the good/bad perception toward the service delivery might be encouraged by the customer satisfaction itself (Kirom, 2010, pp 1-2).

METHOD

The study was a qualitative research using the descriptive approach and the constructivist paradigm. Within the conduct of the study, the method that had been adopted was the descriptive qualitative method. From the relevance of the objective within the conduct of a qualitative study, the study was conducted in order to identify the phenomenon that the subjects had experienced such as behaviours, perceptions, motivations, and actions by means of words and language description in the specifically scientific context by means of numerous scientific methods utilization. In order to attain the accurate data and information, there should be relevant information since information is very vital and, therefore, without information the conduct of any study might be prone to failure. As a result, in order to attain more complete and accurate data, and in order to support the conduct of the study in accordance to the data triangulation technique, there should be key informants and informants. Within the conduct of the study, there were several key informants and informants who had been selected namely: (1) Mr. Baihaqi Halongangan, the CEO & the Director of Enji Multimedia Production House in South Jakarta as the first key informant was; (2) Mr. Sukron Arief, the Account Executive, who had been responsible for the customer service of Enji Multimedia Production House, as the second key informant; (3) Mr. Moussad T., the Field Coordinator, as the first informant; and (4) Anastasya F, the customers or the service use of Enji Multimedia Production House, as the second informant. The key informants and the informants served as the subjects of the study in the in-depth interview and the study was conducted in South Jakarta.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, the researchers would like to elaborate the results of the study that has been conducted in order to answer the problem formulations that have been proposed. Within the conduct of the study, there are several methods that have been implemented in order to answer the problem formulations that have been proposed in the study entitled "Excellent Service Activities of Enji Multimedia Production House in Impression Building." Departing from the background of the study, Enji Multimedia Production House belongs to the category of service-providing company located in South Jakarta that caters to the delivery of the excellent service in Indonesia. This company is also part of the advanced companies amidst the increasingly dynamic market competition. In this kind of competition, excellent service quality should be possessed in order to maintain the customer trust toward the company. Then, the overall results of the study will be elaborated into several sub-sections as follows.

Excellent Service Activities in Enji Multimedia Production House

In performing the excellent service activities, there are several components that should be elaborated and one of these components is certainly the service itself. In this regard, service refers to an action or a performance that one individual delivers to another. Then, service might be classified into two categories namely the high contact service and the low contact service. In order to analyse the excellent service delivery, the problems that take place within its delivery should be investigated. In the context of Enji Multimedia Production House, the excellent service delivery has resulted in various forms of well-qualified service products that have been well known among the public.

The development of the excellent service in numerous service-providing companies nowadays has been more advanced and sophisticated. At the same time, many efforts have been pursued by the businessmen in order to improve the quality of not the product but also the service delivery to the customer. Indeed, identifying the problems becomes the preliminary step for the owner or the CEO of accompany in delivering the excellent service to the customers in order to build the positive impression. Specific to the context of Enji Multimedia Production House, the company has implemented the excellent service delivery since the implementation of the excellent service delivery is an obligation for the part of the company and, not to mention, the company has been operating the domain of service product manufacture. With regards to its nature, Enji Multimedia Production House should deliver the well-qualified service to the customers. Up to date, the customers have witnessed that they are well served from the beginning of their appointment with the company. If the customers have been served well and their desires have been met then the customers will have displayed their satisfaction and given good evaluation to the company (an interview with Mr. Halongangan, the CEO of Enji Multimedia Production House South Jakarta).

In addition to the excellent service delivery, a company should have the standards of the best service delivery to the customers and should not discriminate the customers especially in relation to the project. This statement mainly applies to the companies that have been operating in the domain of service. The customers of these companies demand that they want to take part in the project although some of them decide to handover the completion of the project to the companies. Then, within the completion of a project, these companies usually have a special team that has been assigned to find ideas or creativity in packaging the projects that the clients have proposed (an interview with Mr. Arief, the Account Executive of Enji Multimedia Production House South Jakarta).

The company advancement in the domain of service products has been increasingly developing and up to date there have been so many changes that take place within the delivering of the best service to the customers. In relation to the statement, the excellent service that the customers have perceived is the main value that should be pursued by any company including the Enji Multimedia Production House. Indeed, excellent service that a company should possess is a compulsory procedure especially in serving the customers sincerely and enthusiastically in the best way possible (an interview with Anastasya F., a customer of Enji Multimedia Production House).

Enji Multimedia Production House is a company that operates in the domain of service product manufacture by combing the art design and the interactive multimedia through the utilization of high-end technology. The company was established in 2014 by Mr. Baihaqi Halongangan. The Enji Multimedia Production House has been committed to provide the best service to the customers through the manufacture of the service products. Within one month, the Enji Multimedia Production House has received the assignments from more than 5 customers under various events and one of these events is GIIASS, which has been held from August 10th until August 20st, 2017, in Ice BSD. Within the service product manufacture process, the Enji Multimedia Production House always has special tricks for serving the customers. For example, the Enji Multimedia Production House sets high priority for the customers who want to use the service of the company rather than its competitors.

The service that the company has provided is in the form of brainstorming and the brainstorming is performed by holding a meeting with the customers in order to observe their needs. By doing so, the company will be able to provide the solutions and the offers that might answer the customers' needs (an interview with Moussad, the Field Coordinator of Enji Multimedia Production House, South Jakarta). The competitive edge of the Enji Multimedia Production House within the excellent service delivery lies in the products that the company has manufactured. In general, the products that have been manufactured always result in the high level of satisfaction among the customers and meet the customers' needs and demands. The company has always been in maximum efforts within the excellent service delivery from the beginning until the end. The maximum efforts themselves have been described by: (1) customer-friendly employees; (2) very kind staff; (3) new innovation in each product; (4) willingness to accept complaints from the customers; and (5) provision of best solutions to the customers (an interview with Anastasya F., a customer of Enji Multimedia Production House).

Service quality is an important factor for the success of any service-providing company today. In relation to the statement, the service quality that the company has delivered plays an important role among the customers by meeting the customers' demands and catering to the customers' satisfaction; both of

meeting the customers' demands and catering to the customers' satisfaction have been the top priority for the Enji Multimedia Production House. At the same time, the excellent service has been one of the important strategies for the success and the survival of the company within the increasingly intense competitive in the market. The excellent service delivery itself is assured by providing the progress report during the meeting with the customers, by providing the progress report during the project completion, and by holding an evaluation. The three activities have been compulsory for the creative team of the company so that the company might advance in the future (an interview with Arief Sukron, the Account Executive of Enji Multimedia Production House, South Jakarta).

The presence of the excellent service and its concept that the Enji Multimedia Production House has implemented becomes a responsibility in serving the customers who would like to engage in agreement with the company. On the contrary, the presence of the excellent service and its concept also becomes the demands that the customers have set since the customers want to be provided with the best service by the company. At the same time, the Enji Multimedia Production House has been committed to be all out in completing the assignments that the customers have assigned in their agreement. This is the reason why the products that have been manufactured are always warmly welcomed by the customers.

In delivering the excellent service, the Enji Multimedia Production House has been determined to provide the best service and has also pursued the development of its excellent service delivery by using the emotional approach to the customers in order to influence the impression toward the service that the company has delivered. The activities of the excellent service delivery by the Enji Multimedia Production House South Jakarta might be described as follows:

1. The customers might monitor the implementation of the service delivery activities.
2. The company always involves the competent employees within the service delivery activities.
3. The company provides the best ideas and always engages the customers within the delivery of these ideas.
4. The company always present the sophisticated technology made in Japan and United Kingdom within the service delivery to the customers.
5. The company always sets the deadline for the Vendor Meeting Project.

High Contact Service of Enji Multimedia Production House

In delivering the service to the customers, a company should have the direction that should be achieved by implementing the High Contact Service within the excellent service delivery. The term High Contact Service itself refers to the classification of service delivery in which the contact between the customers and the service providers has been very high; in the High Contact Service, the customers have always been involved in the process of the service delivery. In this regard, the openness of the service provides a clue for informing openly every single detail that has been associated with the service delivery to the customers. In other words, the needs toward the customer service will basically improve the service quality. The presence of the customer engagement facilitates the service delivery process by the company in informing openly the customers' needs.

As having been previously explained in the above paragraph, within the excellent service delivery to the customers the direction that is desired achieve should be made clear by implementing the High Contact Service concept. The objective of the High Contact Service is to bulding positive impression among the customers. Then, within the High Contact Service-based excellent service delivery, the company should participate in the service products that will be manufactured. In addition, the customers should also participate by monitoring the implementation of the service delivery through the recruitment of competent employees, the provision of new ideas, the engagement of the customers within the undergoing projects, the presentation of sophisticated technology made inJapan and United Kingdom, and the conduct of Vendor Meeting Project.

With the engagement of the customers in the project, the Enji Multimedia Production House will be able to identify the preliminary needs of the customers. For instance, through the engagement of the customers in the project the Enji Multimedia Production House might ask about the desired theme, the targeted segment, and the available budget for the intended event (an interview with Mr. Baihaqi Halongangan, the CEO of Enji Multimedia Production House South Jakarta). Such questions are raised in front of the customers in order to identify what the Enji Multimedia Production House might offer, e.g.: the menu that the customers need in the event. Furthermore, by asking such questions the company might

identify the segment or the category of the clients as well as the desire of the client so that the company will provide the ideas that are in line with their brand (an interview with Mr. Baihaqi Halongangan, the CEO of Enji Multimedia Production House South Jakarta).

In implementing the excellent service delivery, the process of the excellent service delivery has been well accepted by the customers. As a result, the customers are satisfied with the performance of the Enji Multimedia Production House by showing positive response. With the engagement of the Account Executive, the company might exert its responsibility upon the customer service. The, within its implementation, the excellent service should be delivered accurately and in accordance to the standard operating procedures of the company namely fast, accurate, and novel within the service product manufacture. Furthermore, according to the standards that have been set, the Enji Multimedia Production House only recruits the distinguished employees with the credibility and the capacity of handling the undergoing project.

In building the company impression among the customers, the Enji Multimedia Production House always strives to provide the best service in accordance to the customers' desires. Consequently, the customers perceive that they have been the top priority of the company and therefore they are always delighted to use the service of the company. Furthermore, the Enji Multimedia Production House always manufactures the well-qualified service products so that the perception of being prioritized by the company among the customers is always reinforced every time the customers are engaged into an agreement with the company. The situation is apparent since the employees of the Enji Multimedia Production House South Jakarta, especially the CEO, the Account Executive, and the Field Coordinator, has always engaged the customers directly within the excellent service delivery. The high credibility among the employees of the Enji Multimedia Production House, especially the Account Executive, is apparent as well in the service products that have been manufactured. The manufacture of the well-qualified service products itself might not be separated from the composition of the team in each project, which consists of: (1) Account Executive; (2) Client Service; (3) Field Coordinator; (4) Field Person in Charge; (5) Installment Person in Charge; and (6) Quality Control Officer. These persons are responsible for each project that has been undergone.

Within the project that has been handled, coordination with the customers should be established in the best way possible with regards to the products that will be manufactured. Occasionally, the customers or the clients will be engaged in both the pre-production stage and the production stage before the projects are executed and eventually displayed (an interview with Sukron Azwar, the Account Executive of Enji Multimedia Production House, who has been responsible for the service delivery, on October 2nd, 2017). In this regard, the company, specifically the employees, and the teams should be able to explain the necessary information to the customers or the clients. Not to mention, the engagement of the customers into the project is compulsory in order that the customers will be comfortable and display satisfaction since their needs are catered. Within the engagement itself, the employees provide full freedom for the customers within each project that has been assigned. In turn, the implementation of High Contact service might result in the positive impression toward the company.

The High Contact Service is provided in the form of product. However, the level of the service delivery is equal from one customer to another. In order to build the positive impression before the customers, the company should provide freedom of engagement to the customers within the service delivery. However, the provision of the engagement should be in accordance to the company procedures. The objective of such provision is to ensure the sense of trust and the convenience on the part of the customers so that the customers perceive the great fulfillment of their desires from the pre-production stage until the post-production stage. In other words, the implementation of the High Contact Service in which the employees of a company provide freedom to the customers within the service delivery will return in the customers' satisfaction and, automatically, the good company impression. The customer engagement in a service-providing company is an important strategy in order that the company might easily explain the product and the customers might easily state their needs and desires. By doing so, the company will be able to contain and map the necessary information (an interview with Sukron Azwar Arief, the Account Executive of Enji Multimedia Production House South Jakarta). In addition, through the customer engagement the team might easily establish field coordination with the customers in relation to their desires so that proper solutions might be identified (an interview with Moussad, the Field Coordinator of Enji Multimedia Production House South Jakarta).

The excellent service provides huge advantage for the company and one of these huge advantages has been quality improvement and positive impression before the customers. For the service-providing company, excellent service serves as the reference of quality development. Therefore, any single detail that might delight the customers in terms of their desire fulfillment becomes the part of the strategy that should be implemented within the excellent service delivery. Not to mention, the excellent service delivery to the customers indeed aims at gaining profit and good reputation for the company. The activities that a service-providing company performs should be associated with the delivery of good and well-structured service so that there will be harmonious cooperation between the service-providing company and the client. All of these activities should depart from cooperation with the companies that have already had well-known brands in order that the company needs might be fulfilled. At the same time, there should be face-to-face communication, which is highly necessary for the establishment of such cooperation.

Up to this point, it might be concluded that excellent service is ultimately important for a service-providing company since excellent service is able to support the company impression and reputation among the customers. At the same time, excellent service is also able to assist or facilitate the customers in opening dialogues from one company to another especially when the company has the well-qualified excellent service. Thus, excellent service might be considered well-qualified when the given service-providing company has recruited the competent employees in each project that the customers have assigned. Specific to the context of the study, in terms of excellent service delivery it is already apparent that the employees of the Enji Multimedia Production House have been attentive and responsible for their customers by providing service alternatives through the hands of the competent employees.

Consequently, in terms of two aspects, namely the aspect of theory and the aspects of practice, it might be viewed that the company has always engaged the customers within the service delivery from the beginning until the end of the event. All types of excellent service delivery have been good and have been in accordance to the standards that the Enji Multimedia Production House has defined. In the High Contact Service, all of the indicators that the Enji Multimedia Production House displays have fallen into the “Good” category. The “Good” category is specifically apparent in the tools that have been operated for manufacturing the new service products and in the sophisticated technology that have been utilized within the service delivery.

Low Contact Service of Enji Multimedia Production House

The implementation of the Low Contact Service might be viewed from the delivery of the excellent service activities in each company. The term Low Contact Service refers to the classification of the service delivery in which the contact between the customers and the service-providing companies is not too high. The example of this concept might be found the physical service delivery to the customers that only take place in the front desk.

With regards to the Low Contact Service, the excellent service activities that the Enji Multimedia Production House South Jakarta have performed are as follows: (1) customers are only allowed to provide suggestions; (2) customers are only allowed to provide company support; (3) customers are only provided with the information around the tools or the technology that will be operated; and (4) customers are only allowed to rent tools for the needs of an event. The Low Contact Service in the form of tool rental or media rental within the delivery of the excellent service as having been performed by the Enji Multimedia Production House is not a new thing. However, when the customers or the clients do not go directly to the company, the Enji Multimedia Production House will give some time for the customers to share their suggestions about the tools that will be operated or the other aspects. In addition, the customers are also invited to provide support for both the employees and the company. On the contrary, with regards to the information about the tools or the technology that will be operated, the customers only need to wait for the briefing by the company or the explanation about the ideas of the company. The explanation about these ideas are usually based on the experience with the previous customers so that the new customers will have better description on the performance of the Enji Multimedia Production House (an interview with Baihaqi Halongangan, the CEO of Enji Multimedia Production South Jakarta).

The Enji Multimedia Production House views that service quality has become increasingly important because in the present time the dynamic has increasingly shifted. The digital world has been easily accessed by anyone and, as a result, the informativeness and the critical thinking of an individual has started to appear

to the surface. Consequently, an individual will easily complain and be critical toward the improper policies or service deliveries within a company. With reference to the situation, the critical attitude might also be resulted the service products that have been manufactured and therefore the customers might have decided to purchase or to not purchase the given service products. The reason is that the customers demand well-qualified service as they decide to purchase the service products of a company. In this light, the excellent service should be able to cater the customers appropriately and responsively in a sense that the service delivery should be in accordance to the company objective. Actually, the context of Low Contact Service might be easily implemented by the employees in any company. For example, the employees might explain the ideas that have been implemented in the company so that it will be easier for these employees to convince the customers about the service that have used to be delivered and to gain success upon the service that the company has offered (an interview with Moussad, the Field Coordinator of Enji Multimedia Production House South Jakarta).

These ideas are discussed when the customers come to the company and meet the PIC or the AE of the company. In this discussion, the customers share their desires and when the customers have shared their desires the team of the Enji Multimedia Production House will explain the idea or the description of the event that will be held. Every PIC or AE of the team is responsible from the beginning until the end of the project. Therefore, the responsibility of all employees is put together in the project that the Enji Multimedia Production House has handled; however, the PIC responsible for the project should debrief the field staffs. In this case, the employees become the determining factor for the survival of the company since the employees lay the fundamental foundation in the customer service delivery. Due to this nature, the employees should be polite, courteous, responsible, patient. Then, in the service delivery activities, the employees should be able to serve the agreement from the beginning until the end of the cooperation process in the service domain that the Enji Multimedia Production House has offered. According to the procedures in the company, every employed is demanded to deliver the necessary service to every single customer that comes to the company. The service delivery itself should be in such a way that the customers' needs should be catered, the customers' needs should be easily facilitated, and there should be any single mistake within the service delivery.

Excellent service constitutes the reflection of a company that puts forward the customer satisfaction by delivering equal service and recruiting highly credible employees. The delivery of equal service and the recruitment of highly credible employees are parts of the main values among the customers. If a company is able to satisfy the parties that should be served, then a good impression will be formed among the customers. Thus, the presence of the realistic objective becomes compulsory within the direction-planning process and the focus toward the objectives that have been defined. In doing so, the objectives that have been defined might be achieved by delivering the excellent service to the customers and the excellent delivery itself might build the customer trust. With regard to the concept of Low Contact Service, the Enji Multimedia Production House always delivers the best service to all customers and is always sincere in serving and facilitating the customers' needs of information; this aspect has been the top priority of the company. Therefore, there should be continuous cooperation not only in one event but also in the following events that might take place in both near and far future. This aspect is also important to maintain since customer expectation plays a significant role in the product quality and service delivery. Indeed, the customers rely on their expectation as the standards or the reference in evaluating the successful excellent service delivery of a company. By delivering the maximum service, a company is able to provide a sense of security and convenience among the customers and is also able to create customer satisfaction toward the product. In turn, the customers will develop their willingness to be engaged again in the cooperation with the company or in the purchase decision toward the products of the company.

CONCLUSIONS

Departing from the results and the discussions that have been elaborated in the previous section, there are several conclusions that might be drawn in relation to the branding impression building. First of all, excellent service has an important role within a company especially in the efforts of building the branding impression. As one of the service-providing companies in the South Jakarta region that cares about the implementation of excellent service delivery in Indonesia, the Enji Multimedia Production House features and sets priority for the customers in order to deliver the satisfaction and the solution for the customers in

handling the projects together. Then, excellent service activities that the Enji Multimedia Production House South Jakarta have implemented are as follows: (1) allowing the customers to monitor the implementation of the service delivery activities; (2) recruiting the employees who have competence in the domain of service delivery; (3) delivering new ideas by engaging the customers; (4) delivering the service through the sophisticated technology made in Japan and United Kingdom to the customers; and (5) setting the deadline for the Vendor Meeting Project.

Then, delivering the excellent service to the customers has been the priority with regards to the best service delivery in accordance with the needs, the satisfaction, and the events of the customers. Through the excellent service delivery, the sense of satisfaction upon the performance of the Enji Multimedia Production House might be created.

Furthermore, the Enji Multimedia Production House has delivered the service based on the concept of High Contact Service. Such service delivery is carried out by engaging the customers in the service products that will be offered. In addition, the customers might monitor the implementation of the service delivery, the recruitment of the competent employees, the delivery of new ideas in the undergoing events, the utilization of sophisticated technology made in Japan and United Kingdom, the setting the deadlines for the Vendor Meeting Project. The customers are even engaged in the service delivery of each stage. On the other hand, in relation to the concept of High Contact Service, the Enji Multimedia Production House has also implemented the concept of Low Contact Service. The Low Contact Service is apparent from the following activities: (1) customers are only allowed to provide suggestions; (2) customers are only allowed to provide company support; (3) customers are only provided with the information around the tools or the technology that will be operated; and (4) customers are only allowed to rent the tools for the needs of an event. In sum, it might be asserted that the Enji Multimedia Production House has dominantly implemented the High Contact Service rather than the Low Contact Service since both of the company and the customers have taken participation within the excellent service delivery.

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